

ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL FOUNDATIONS OF COOPERATION BETWEEN CRIME PREVENTION SERVICES AND OTHER STATE BODIES

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In recent years, systematic efforts have been undertaken in our country to ensure human rights, enhance accountability and transparency of state authorities, and strengthen the role of civil society institutions, mass media, political engagement of the population, and public associations.

In particular, based on an in-depth analysis of complex global processes and the country's development results in recent years, the **Development Strategy "From the Strategy of Actions to the Development Strategy" for 2022–2026** was formulated, encompassing seven priority areas. It is aimed at further improving the well-being of the people under the principle "**In the Name of Human Dignity**", transforming economic sectors, accelerating entrepreneurship development, ensuring the absolute protection of human rights and interests, and fostering an active civil society.

In this **Development Strategy of "New Uzbekistan" for 2022–2026**, the **principle of the rule of law and justice** has been identified as the second priority area, as it is recognized as the most fundamental and necessary condition for the country's development. This highlights that **ensuring justice and the rule of law is one of the key priorities of state policy**.

The main task of any democratic state is to ensure the **protection of human rights, freedoms, and legal interests**. From this perspective, **the interaction of crime prevention services with other state bodies in carrying out preventive activities in society has become one of the most pressing issues**.

One of the main forms of governance is **cooperation**, the essential condition of which is **coordination and joint organization of specific activities**.

No state body or organization can ensure the **efficiency of its activities** relying solely on **internal resources**, without **interacting with other structures**.

Therefore, before discussing **cooperation between crime prevention services and other state bodies**, it is appropriate to first define **the activities of these services**.

The **Crime Prevention Service** operates in accordance with the **Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention" and "On Internal Affairs Bodies,"** as well as **Presidential Decrees**:

- № PF-6196 of March 26, 2021 – "On Measures to Elevate the Activities of Internal Affairs Bodies in Ensuring Public Safety and Combating Crime to a New Qualitative Level";
- № PF-27 of November 29, 2021 – "On the Approval of the Concept of Public Security of the Republic of Uzbekistan and Measures for Its Implementation," as well as **other regulatory legal acts**.

In accordance with these **normative documents**, the **Main Directorate for Crime Prevention of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan** was reorganized into the **Crime Prevention Service** within the **Department of Public Security of the Ministry of Internal Affairs**.

The structure of the **Crime Prevention Service** is **conditionally divided into central, regional, and local levels (Republic – Region – District – Mahalla)**:

1. **Central (Republican) Level** – The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Department of Public Security, and the Crime Prevention Service within it.

2. **Regional (Provincial and District) Level** – The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Karakalpakstan, the Main Departments of Internal Affairs of Tashkent city and Tashkent region, regional Departments of Internal Affairs, district and city departments (divisions) of internal affairs, and the Crime Prevention Units within the Public Security Service.

3. **Local (Mahalla) Level** – Mahalla public safety centers and support points of internal affairs bodies, which include **senior, chief, and junior prevention inspectors**.

The **Crime Prevention Services** function under the principle of **vertical subordination**, ensuring **integrated management and continuous control**. Their activities are based on the **Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Crime Prevention" dated May 14, 2014**. The primary tasks of the service include **ensuring and strengthening public order, identifying and suppressing offenses, determining and eliminating the causes and conditions conducive to offenses**.

The **crime prevention system** includes **general, special, individual, and victimological prevention**, as well as a set of **legal, social, organizational, and other measures aimed at crime prevention**.

Additionally, according to **Cabinet of Ministers Resolution № 801 of November 30, 2024**, "On Measures to Improve the Efficiency of the Social Prevention System in Mahallas Based on the '**Prosperous and Safe Mahalla**' Principle," crime prevention services also implement **social prevention measures at the local level**.

The **key directions** for enhancing the efficiency of **crime prevention** were outlined in **Presidential Decree № PQ-2896 of April 18, 2017**, "On Measures for the Fundamental Improvement of the Activities of Crime Prevention Units of the Internal Affairs Bodies." According to this decree, the **Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan** and its **territorial subdivisions** were assigned the following **key tasks**:

- Establishing a **new qualitative order of work for crime prevention units at all levels (republican, regional, and district)**.
- Clearly defining the **main tasks, functions, and responsibilities of prevention units**.
- Preventing the **assignment of unrelated duties** to prevention inspectors.
- Organizing **preventive work in close cooperation with the public, self-government bodies, and civil society institutions**.
- **Prioritizing early detection and prevention of offenses**.
- **Raising legal culture in society, fostering respect for the law and intolerance for violations**.
- **Developing a system of work with minors and youth**.
- **Instilling patriotism, respect for national and universal values in young people**.

- **Protecting the younger generation from terrorism, religious extremism, violence, and cruelty.**
 - **Strengthening the personal responsibility** of prevention inspectors for their duties.
 - **Introducing a systematic public accountability mechanism** for inspectors.
 - **Eliminating a formal approach** to resolving public concerns.
 - **Implementing effective criteria** for evaluating the **performance of prevention inspectors.**
 - **Taking into account public opinion and citizens' satisfaction** with their work.
 - **Assessing the level of interaction** between **inspectors and the population.**
 - **Expanding the use of modern information and communication technologies** in **crime prevention services.**
 - **Enhancing knowledge and professional training** of prevention inspectors.
 - **Improving working conditions, providing service housing** in assigned areas.
 - **Introducing financial incentives** for inspectors for **successful task completion.**
- Crime prevention services carry out their tasks **in close cooperation with other state bodies.**

Literature:

1. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Конституцияси // Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 01.05.2023 й., 03/23/837/0241-сон / <https://lex.uz/docs/6445145>
2. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2014 йил 14 майдаги “Хуқуқбузарликлар профилактикаси тўғрисида”ги ЎРҚ-371-сон Қонуни / <https://lex.uz/docs/2387357>
3. Ўзбекистон Республикасининг 2016 йил 16 сентябрдаги “Ички ишлар органлари тўғрисида”ги ЎРҚ-407-сон Қонуни / <https://lex.uz/docs/3027843>
4. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2022 йил 28 январдаги “2022 — 2026 йилларга мўлжалланган Янги Ўзбекистоннинг тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида”ги ПФ-60-сон Фармони / <https://lex.uz/docs/5344118>
5. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2021 йил 29 ноябрдаги “Ўзбекистон Республикаси жамоат хавфсизлиги концепциясини тасдиқлаш ва уни амалга ошириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПФ-27-сон Фармони / <https://lex.uz/docs/5749291>
6. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2017 йил 18 апрелдаги “Ички ишлар органларининг хуқуқбузарликлар профилактикаси бўлинмалари фаолиятини тубдан такомиллаштириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги ПҚ-2896-сон Қарори / <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/3175732>
7. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Вазирлар Маҳкамасининг 30.11.2024 йил 30 ноябрдаги “Обод ва хавфсиз маҳалла” тамойили асосида маҳаллаларда ижтимоий профилактика тизими самарадорлигини ошириш чора-тадбирлари тўғрисида”ги 801-сон қарори / <https://www.lex.uz/docs/7243832>
8. Ахмедов Ҳ.Э. Маъмурий назорат остидаги шахсларга оид профилактик чора-тадбирларни такомиллаштириш / юридик фанлар бўйича фалсафа доктори (Doctor of Philosophy) илмий даражасини олиш учун тайёрланган диссертация иши / Тошкент – 2021. Б. 78.
9. Бобохонов А.А. Жамоат тартибини сақлаш ва фуқаролар хавфсизлигини таъминлашда хуқуқни муҳофаза қилувчи органларнинг ўзаро ҳамкорлиги // Жамоат

- тартибини сақлаш ва фуқаролар хавфсизлигини таъминлашнинг долзарб масалалари: республика илмий-амалий конференция материаллари. – Т.: ЎЗР ИИБ Академияси, 2015. – Б. 11.
10. Афанасьев В.А. Организация работы участкового инспектора милиции. – М., 1990. – С. 38.
11. Зиёдуллаев М.З. Ички ишлар органларининг таянч пунктларини бошқаришни такомиллаштириш: Монография. – Т.: Ўзбекистон Республикаси ИИБ Академияси, 2018. – Б. 173.
12. Исмаилов И. Терроризмга қарши кураш // Қонун ҳимоясида. – 2004. – № 7. – Б. 30.
13. Нечевина Н.Д. Правовое регулирование участия граждан в обеспечении правопорядка в современный период / Под ред. А.З. Гливинского. – М., 2006. – С. 59;
14. Яблоков И.П. Взаимодействие народных дружин и милиции. – М., 1977. – С. 27;
15. Полищук А.Д. Взаимодействие милиции с добровольными народными дружинами в сфере охраны общественного порядка. Административно-правовой аспект. – Киев, 1981. – С. 63;
16. Колпаков В.К. Взаимодействие участковых инспекторов милиции с формированиями общественности. – Киев, 1990. – С. 35.
17. Зарипов З.С. Профилактическая функция следственных подразделений органов внутренних дел. – Т., 1980. – С. 57.
18. И.Исмаилов, М.Зиёдуллаев, Н.Исроилова, Ф.Азимова. Вояга етмаганлар назоратсизлиги ва ҳуқуқбузарликларининг олдини олиш: ўқув-амалий кўлланма / масъул муҳаррир И. Исмаилов. – Т.: Республика болалар ижтимоий мослашуви маркази, 2011. Б. 10.
19. Umirzakov , B. ., & Boltayev , M. . (2024). Retsidiv jinoyatchilikning kriminologik tavsifi va oldini olishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari. Евразийский журнал академических исследований, 4(4), 175–184. извлечено от <https://inacademy.uz/index.php/ejar/article/view/30229> DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11001121>
20. К.Р. Абдурасулова, Б.А. Умирзаков - ... криминологии, криминалистики и ..., 2019 - elibrary.ru Криминологическая характеристика и профилактика преступности несовершеннолетних в Республике Узбекистан
21. Umirzakov B. Analysis of legislation on the prevention of juvenile delinquency in developed foreign countries //The American Journal of Political Science Law and Criminology. – 2022. – Т. 4. – №. 01. – С. 66-72.
22. Умирзаков Б. Оила-турмуш доирасидаги ҳуқуқбузарликларнинг тушунчаси //Общественные науки в современном мире: теоретические и практические исследования. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. Maxsus son. – С. 166-170.
23. Умирзаков Б. А., Болтаев М. М. Surxondaryo viloyatida oila-turmush doirasidagi jinoyatchilikning kriminologik tavsifi va oldini olishni takomillashtirish //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2024. – Т. 4. – №. 5-3. – С. 42-53.
24. Саъдуллаев Гайрат Абдужаббор Угли, Хамракулов Лочинбек Эркинжон Угли ГОСУДАРСТВЕННАЯ ПОЛИТИКА РЕСПУБЛИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАН В ОБЛАСТИ ПРОТИВОДЕЙСТВИЯ ПРЕСТУПЛЕНИЯМ В СФЕРЕ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И БЕЗОПАСНОСТИ // EJAR. 2024. №5-3. URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/gosudarstvennaya-politika-respubliki-uzbekistan-v->

oblasti-protivodeystviya-prestupleniyam-v-sfere-tsifrovyyh-tehnologiy-i
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